

PHIRI FORESIGHT: MODELLING & SCENARIOS

Insight into future trends and developments is essential for the everyday work of policy makers. Foresight is a systematic, participatory, and vision-building process that explores the future with the aim to anticipate future trends and support present-day actions. The COVID-19 pandemic emphasized the importance of **Public Health Foresight Studies (PHFS)**. PHFS are more necessary than ever to gain insight into possible future health impacts of pandemics, in the short and long term. These include impacts on regular healthcare delivery, lifestyle and socio-economic status.

The overall aim is to support European Union Member States (EU MS) in conducting a public health foresight study in order to gain insights into possible future health impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Results

1. OVERVIEW OF CURRENT FORESIGHT ACTIVITIES IN EUROPE AND BEYOND

Through a literature review and a survey, we identified current foresight activities and gained knowledge regarding the capacity and need for foresight methodology. In addition, we were able to create a foresight network. Our inventory of foresight activities from the survey showed that only a few EU MS had an established capacity to conduct foresight studies. The survey shed light on the foresight capacity needs across EU MS, which served as basis to develop the foresight capacity building course.

2. CAPACITY BUILDING IN FORESIGHT

We developed a public health foresight course to level EU MS to a similar degree of knowledge in foresight to strengthen European capacity in foresight. The course took place in 2021 and reached more than 70 public health professionals across 21 EU MS. The course consisted of three parts; an introductory module, a set of three advanced modules, and a final module synthesizing the lessons learned. The foresight methodology template and course videos are available for public use, in order to further disseminate and strengthen foresight capacity.

3. USING THIS CAPACITY TO DEVELOP SCENARIOS

We developed the capacity building activity 'Develop your PHFS' in which participants from EU MS conducted their own foresight study with support from PHIRI. 'Develop your PHFS' took place throughout 2022, consisting of 12 guided sessions and resulted in 11 country foresight studies from 8 EU MS. Participants further developed their knowledge, expertise, and capacity in public health foresight. This activity also shed light into challenges that can be encountered during the planning and development of a foresight study and how to address such challenges.

4. DEVELOPING GUIDANCE IN IDENTIFYING PROMISING POLICY STRATEGIES

Based on the lessons learnt from the previous tasks, four policy briefs were developed. These policy briefs focused on the use of foresight in policy-making and aimed to communicate to public health experts and policy makers on how foresight can provide a platform to explore the future and discuss possible solutions to address present and future challenges towards desirable futures. Three policy briefs provided specific examples on the use of foresight and resulting policy recommendations in mental health, climate change and healthcare, and digitalization of healthcare.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of foresight in public health and health policy is gaining importance but still needs further development to fully benefit from its use in policy making. Foresight can provide a platform to explore present and future challenges, improve democratic processes, and contribute to implementing policies and interventions in the present towards desirable futures and improved health outcomes.

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